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Comparison Between The Efficacy Of Cimt And Ndt On Upper Extremity Rehabilitation Among Patients Of Stroke

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Article Details

ABSTRACT

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Background: Stroke is one of the leading causes of disability worldwide, affecting millions annually, with significant resultant deficits particularly the motor deficit in upper extremities. Constraint Induced Movement Therapy (CIMT) and Neuro-Developmental Treatment (NDT) are specialized rehabilitation approaches aiming at motor recovery among stroke survivors.

Objectives: This double blinded RCT compares the effectiveness of CIMT and NDT among stroke patients, having conventional physiotherapy as a baseline to address the critical literature gap.

Patients and Methods: Ten participants, aged 40-65 years were recruited using purposive sampling technique and were randomly assigned to two treatment groups. Both groups attended a rehabilitation program of 6 weeks. Pre and Post treatment motor function was assessed using motor assessment scale and spasticity levels were assessed using Modified Ashworth Scale. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS 27 considering a p value ≥ 0.05 as statistically significant.

Results: Results indicated a significant improvement in the motor function for the CIMT group (mean MAS score increased from 16.2 ± 7.3 to 31.8 ± 9.4) compared to the NDT one (11.2 ± 6.5 to 15.4 ± 5.9). Both groups demonstrated a significant reduction in levels of spasticity, though inter group differences were not statistically significant. Additionally, a transfer of training effect was also observed, with moderate improvement in motor function of lower extremity.

Conclusions: This study concludes that CIMT is superior to NDT in motor recovery.

INTRODUCTION:

Stroke or Cerebro Vascular Accident is a leading cause of long term morbidity and mortality all around the globe, with significant impact on motor control and function, especially in the upper extremity. It is estimated that annually stroke affects 15 million people globally(1), with an approximation of 5 million deaths and another 5 million people left with severe and permanent disabilities.(2) Among the survivors, about 50-70% individuals experience mild disability and about 30% of individuals suffer moderate to severe disability that greatly hinders their ability to perform ADLs(3). Stroke is the second leading cause of mortality around the globe, accounting for 11% of total deaths. The chronic disability association with stroke is also critical, with about 26% survivors never regaining functional control of the upper extremity. In Pakistan, the incidence of stroke is alarmingly high, with about 250,000 cases annually, affecting 4.8% of the adult population(4). In Pakistan about 40% of the stroke affected patients experience chronic functional dysfunction, and limited availability of rehabilitation and physiotherapy services further exacerbates this burden.

Motor deficit in upper extremity is one of the most common residual impairments following stroke, taking a heavy toll on the patient's quality of life.(5) Physiotherapy and other rehabilitation interventions, therefore, play a crucial role in recovery, with various approaches aiming to improve and restore function and control.(6)

Post Stroke Hemiparesis, particularly in the upper extremity, is a major challenge in restoring functional independence. Rehabilitation is focused on regaining motor control, muscle strength and proprioception and movement coordination, primarily aimed to enable the patient to resume ADLs. There are a variety of rehabilitation protocols available for stroke rehabilitation. Some of the commonly used and more effective strategies are conventional physiotherapy, constraint induced movement therapy CIMT, and neurodevelopmental treatment NDT.(7)

Conventional Physiotherapy includes a wide range of interventions, ranging from active and passive range of motions, stretching and strengthening techniques to task specific exercises. Although conventional physiotherapy is widely known and used, it may lack intensity and specificity observed in targeted therapies. Nonetheless, conventional physiotherapy has demonstrated significant importance in stroke rehabilitation by improving motor function and independence.(8)

Constraint Induced Movement Therapy is a targeted therapy aimed to improve the active use of the stroke affected limb by restraining the sound limb. CIMT is designed to counteract the learned disuse of the affected limb by encouraging repetitive practice of the functional activities. Studies have demonstrated CIMT's efficacy in restoration and improving upper extremity function through cortical reorganization phenomena. When compared to conventional physiotherapy, CIMT has been particularly effective, leading to significant improvements in motor function and coordination.(9)

Neurodevelopmental Treatment, also known as Bobath Approach, is also a targeted therapy, focused on improving abnormal postural patterns and facilitating natural movement patterns by reducing muscular tone, enhancing neuromuscular coordination and integrating sensory stimulation with motor control. This hands-on intervention is widely used in stroke rehabilitation, with evidence suggesting its success in reduction of compensatory movements. Like CIMT, NDT has also yielded positive results when compared to conventional physiotherapy.(10)

To objectively and accurately assess the efficacy of these treatment regimes, reliable assessment tools are of critical importance. In this research study, Motor Assessment Scale(11) was employed to evaluate motor function and recovery, cognitive status and spasticity among stroke survivors.

Motor Assessment Scale is a commonly used tool to assess motor function among stroke survivors. It grades various domains of physical activity, including upper extremity movements(12). Studies have reported an 84% sensitivity and a 90% specificity of MAS especially when evaluating upper extremity function post stroke.(13)

Spasticity is a common consequence of stroke and Modified Ashworth Scale is an important tool to assess it

during passive soft tissue stretching(14). Modified Ashworth Scale is known to have a sensitivity of 50% and a specificity of 92%(15).

While both CIMT and NDT have been independently and individually compared to Conventional Physiotherapy, there is a significant literature gap that directly compares CIMT and NDT. Both therapies have distinct theoretical principles and both are known to be affective post stroke, yet the relative efficacy remains unclear.

This research aims to fill important gaps in stroke rehabilitation by delivering a comprehensive comparison between both, the programmed Constraint-Induced Movement Therapy (CIMT) and Neurodevelopmental Treatment (NDT) alongside the conventional physiotherapy. By identifying the most beneficial form of evidenced-based rehabilitation method for the re-establishment of upper limb function, this study will have a direct impact on the affordability of care of the patients to ensure that they are under the best form of therapy from the start and therefore optimize the recovery time and increase long-term outcomes. Furthermore, results will enhance current trends in physiotherapy practice by empowering clinicians with optimised, patient-centred approach strategies and refined handling techniques. Ultimately, the goal of this work is to create awareness among healthcare professionals on specific therapeutic benefits of each approach resulting in a more informed and effective rehabilitation landscape for the stroke survivor.

METHODS

It was a double blinded randomized controlled trail carried out in physiotherapy department of Shalamar Institute of Health Sciences, Lahore, Pakistan. The calculated sample size for 2 population means was 16 using G-Power software (16), according to the following calculations,

$$n = \frac{2\sigma^2 \left(z_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}} + z_{1-\beta} \right)^2}{(\mu_1 - \mu_2)^2}$$

- $Z_{1-\alpha/2}$: Level of Significance = 5%
- $Z_{1-\beta}$: Power of the study = 95%
- μ_1 : Expected Mean of CIMT Group = 47.57
- μ_2 : Expected Mean of Control Group = 29.29 (17)

Non probability purposive sampling method was used. 16 stroke patients were divided into two groups (A and B) using random allocation. Group A participants received the CIMT intervention while group B participants underwent NDT. Participants aged 40-65 years, having experienced either a haemorrhagic or ischemic stroke with hemiplegic presentation within the past 1 to 6 months were recruited for the study. Additionally, a Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) score of 23 was considered for inclusion. Participants with visual or auditory deficits, musculoskeletal (MSK) disorders, mental impairments, or a history of surgery were excluded from the study. Participants underwent Constraint-Induced Movement Therapy (CIMT) and Neuro-Developmental Treatment (NDT) for one hour daily over a period of six weeks. The treatment method involved a six-week duration, with sessions scheduled three times per week. Each session lasted for one hour, providing consistent and structured therapeutic engagement throughout the course of the treatment. The motor recovery was assessed using Motor Assessment Scale while Ashworth Scale was administered to document any associated improvement in spasticity post treatment.

RESULTS

The study included a total of 16 participants, with ages ranging from 49 to 58 years, resulting in a mean age of 53.60 years. The standard deviation of 2.88 indicates moderate variability in age, suggesting that participants are predominantly middle-aged with relatively similar ages.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Age of Participants

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean ± Std. Deviation
Age	16	49.00	58.00	53.60 ± 2.86

Table 2: Between Group Analysis of Both Treatment Groups

	Treatment Group	N	Mean ± Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	p-value
Motor Assessment Scale Score Pre-treatment	1 (CIMT)	8	16.20 ± 7.33	3.28	0.288
	2 (NDT)	8	11.20 ± 6.53	2.92	
Motor Assessment Scale Score Post-treatment	1 (CIMT)	8	31.80 ± 9.44	4.22	0.011
	2 (NDT)	8	15.40 ± 5.94	2.66	

The study comprised two treatment groups, each with 8 participants. For the Motor Assessment Scale scores, the pre-treatment results indicated that Group 1 (CIMT Group) had a mean score of **16.20** (standard deviation = **7.33**, standard error = **3.28**), while Group 2 (NDT Group) had a mean score of **11.20** (standard deviation = **6.53**, standard error = **2.92**). In the post-treatment assessments, Group 1 demonstrated a significant improvement with a mean score of **31.80** (standard deviation = **9.44**, standard error = **4.22**), compared to Group 2, which had a mean post-treatment score of **15.40** (standard deviation = **5.94**, standard error = **2.66**). These results suggest that both treatment groups showed improvements, but Group 1 exhibited a notably greater enhancement in motor assessment scores following the intervention.

Table 3: Across Group Analysis of Both Treatment Groups

	Mean ± Standard Deviation	N	Std. Error Mean	p-value
Motor Assessment Scale Score Pre-treatment	13.70 ± 7.06	16	2.23	0.001
Motor Assessment Scale Score Post-treatment	23.60 ± 11.40	16	3.61	

The **p-value of 0.001** suggests that the improvement in MAS scores is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), implying the treatment had a notable effect.

Table 4: Effect of Treatment on Spasticity Levels

	Mean ± Std. Deviation	N	Std. Error Mean	p-value
Ashworth Scale Score Pre-Treatment	1.14 ± 0.76	16	0.24	<0.001
Ashworth Scale Score Post-Treatment	0.59 ± 0.46	16	0.14	

Table shows that the mean Ashworth Scale score decreased from **1.135** (SD = 0.760) pre-treatment to **0.592** (SD = 0.460) post-treatment, indicating a reduction in spasticity. The standard error decreased from **0.240** to **0.145**, suggesting less variability in post-treatment scores. These results suggest that the treatment effectively reduced spasticity among participants.

Table 5: Transfer of Training Effect (Lower Limb Motor Function Assessment)

	Treatment Group	N	Mean ± Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	p-value
Motor Assessment Scale Score Lower Limb Pre-Treatment	1 (CIMT)	8	6.00 ± 4.85	2.17	0.544
	2 (NDT)	8	4.40 ± 2.88	1.29	
Motor Assessment Scale Score Lower Limb Post-Treatment	1 (CIMT)	8	11.00 ± 4.18	1.87	0.067
	2 (NDT)	8	5.80 ± 3.56	1.59	

While both groups showed improvement in lower limb motor function, the CIMT group exhibited more substantial gains compared to the NDT group, as reflected in the higher post-treatment mean score. Although the difference in post-treatment scores was not statistically significant at the 0.05 level, it approached significance, suggesting that CIMT may be more effective than NDT in improving motor function in the lower limb.

DISCUSSION

The current randomized controlled trial aimed to determine the effectiveness of constraint-induced movement therapy (CIMT) and neurodevelopmental treatment (NDT)/Bobath Concept in improving upper-extremity motor functioning during stroke survivors, whilst adjusting the conventional physiotherapy as a possible factor of confounding bias.

As per the modern evidence, the research revealed CIMT to generate considerably higher motor improvements as compared to NDT as shown by superior gains observed in the CIMT group. The implications of these findings as compared to other recent studies on rehabilitation, emphasizing the significance of vigorous and task-based training to promote neuroplasticity and help individuals recover their functions after a stroke, are crucial.

Recent literature documents the positive outcomes of CIMT in rehabilitation of stroke. The systematic reviews and meta-analyses have reported that CIMT regimes result in a significant upper-limb motor outcomes improvement as compared to control regime, especially with appropriate constraint practice and high-repetition practice. As an example, a meta-analysis based on networks found that protocols of CIMT that aimed at maximizing the use of affected limbs produced larger improvements in Fugl-Meyer Upper Extremity scores compared with less vigorous methods.(18)

Moreover, a multicentre randomised trial comparing CIMT plus mirror therapy and standard rehabilitation showed that both of the experimental groups significantly improved their functions, and CIMT showed a tendency to better muscle-strength improvement, but the difference between them was not statistically significant compared with that of the mirror therapy.(19) A second controlled trial carried out in Pakistan showed better increases in hand dexterity and quality of life when using CIMT compared to Bobath over a

period of eight weeks.(20) These results support the continued applicability of intensive, task-focused use of the impacted limb in modern stroke rehabilitation.

These results suggest that intensive, task-specific use of the affected limb remains a significant part of modern stroke rehabilitation.

On the other hand the evidence to back the Bobath/NDT approach is weak and maleficent. The systematic reviews of Bobath therapy against other rehabilitative interventions show that, in spite of the potential motor benefits, NDT does not typically perform better than other task-focused or motor-relearning therapy. Indicatively, after thorough literature search, a randomized clinical trial conducted a comparison between Bobath and a Motor Relearning Programme found that both groups had significant improvements in Fugl-Meyer and Wolf Motor Function Test scores, with Bobath therapy reporting better gains in motor improvement in the study conditions.(21) However, larger reviews show that the Bobath concept does not have strong evidence of improvement over intensive or task-specific stroke treatment in motor recovery, and that NDT is not a priority intervention with regard to rehabilitation guidelines.(22)

This difference could be due to different therapeutic processes: CIMT emphasises high-intensity, repetitive, task-based practice, involving motor-learning and neuroplasticity developing processes, whereas NDT emphasises functional-task gains through normalization of movement patterns, which is not always directly comparable with task-oriented therapies. In addition, the variability of NDT protocols in different clinical settings makes it difficult to standardise and synthesise evidence.

Regardless of the higher motor gains realized through CIMT, the current study also reported a decrease in spasticity in both groups of participants. The average change in the scores of the Modified Ashworth Scale between pre and post treatments indicates that structured rehabilitation (independent of the modality) has a positive impact on muscle tone. Even though the statistically significant difference did not arise between Group 2 and Group 1, the tone reduction observed has clinical implication since spasticity has the potential to deteriorate movement quality and daily activity.

Another observation was the cross-limb transfer of the motor gains to the lower extremities in both groups of therapy although the upper limbs were the focus of interventions. The difference in the lower-extremity motor scores with the CIMT population and the NDT population did not significantly differ, but the trend was favourable toward the CIMT group, as the larger meta-analytic data show that more rigorous CIMT can have a positive effect on lower-limb functions and balance. And, this transfer of the limbs across indicates how closely the neuroplastic response of the nervous system can be tied to one another and indicates that the upper-limb training can be an expression of systemic neurorehabilitative benefit.(23)

Overall, this trial supports the view that CIMT is an effective modality of purposive upper-limb rehabilitation after stroke, as it has better motor outcomes compared to NDT as reported in recent trials. Although NDT might still have a role to play, especially in the early stages of recovery or as part of a hybrid regime, task-based repetitive types of training are gaining more and more support as the optimal way of achieving meaningful functional restoration.

CONCLUSIONS

It was concluded that CIMT has better effects on rehabilitation of upper extremity motor function compared to NDT

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The major limitation in this study was a significantly smaller sample size (n=16), which limits the extent of generalizability of results. Another major limiting factor of our study was the non-probability purposive sampling which renders the results at a stake of sampling bias. Additionally, treatment time of 6 weeks was essentially insufficient for more complex therapies such as neurodevelopmental treatment to display proper results.

However, this study forms a baseline for further more well-structured and more prolonged therapeutic

interventions to come up with more concise and generalizable results.

IMPLICATIONS

The present study shows that constraint-induced movement therapy (CIMT) has better upper-limb motor recovery in comparison with neurodevelopmental treatment (NDT), thus improving functional independence and quality of life among stroke survivors. To neurophysiotherapy practitioners, the results highlight the significance of high-repetition, task-specific, intensive training programmes, and reveal that NDT can be better utilized as an adjunctive intervention to treat spastic tone and postural regulation. Research wise, the findings provoke the need to research more long term retention of motor gains, define optimal CIMT dose parameters, and clarify cross-limb neuroplastic processes, and the need to standardize NDT protocols to be able to compare and contrast results meaningfully and to support evidence-based clinical practice.

FUTURE RESEARCH

The standardization of intervention protocols, the analysis of retention of motor gains over the long term, and study of integrated or hybrid interventions to combine the advantages of high-intensity practice with movement-facilitation principles are the research areas of the future.

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